

Analytical Applications of some Oxidizing Agents in the Determination of Mercaptans

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An accurate direct titrimetric procedure for the determination of mercaptans has been evolved using various oxidizing agents, viz., iodine monochloride, iodine monobromide, iodine trichloride in aqueous solution and iodine cyanide in dilute hydrochloric acid. The end point was determined visually using amylose as indicator or potentiometrically. The procedure is accurate to $\pm 0.3\%$, the precision being $\pm 0.5\%$. Effect of foreign substances has also been studied.

THE ubiquitous sulphhydryl radical has been the subject of much analytical researches. A number of methods for their assay have earlier been proposed which are usually based upon the reaction of active hydrogen of sulphhydryl group or oxidation of the latter to the corresponding disulphide.

Interhalogens have extensively been used in analytical chemistry. The present communication deals with the use of some of interhalogens like ICl, IBr, ICl₃ and BrCl and pseudointerhalogens like ICN and BrCN for determination of mercaptans. The method is based upon the oxidation mercaptans with above mentioned reagents to the appropriate disulphide.

where, X = Cl, or Br, or Cl₃, or CN.

The reaction, being instantaneous, can be used for direct titration of samples and is relatively free from shortcomings.

Experimental

Reagents and Samples :

Aqueous solutions of ICl¹, IBr², ICl₃^{3,4} and ICN⁵ were prepared by dissolving appropriate amount of the sample in one litre so as to give 0.05*N* solution and standardised by adding, to an aliquot of the oxidant, a 10% solution of potassium iodide (alongwith 1 ml of 2*N* HCl in case of iodine cyanide) and titrating the liberated iodine with standard thiosulphate. Each atom of monopositive iodine liberates two equivalents of iodine. Most of the mercaptans were gifts from Evans Chemitics, New York, N.Y. Some samples were prepared and purified by authors⁶.

Toshniwal titration potentiometer type CL-06 equipped with fibre type saturated calomel electrode and a bright platinum electrode was used for potentiometric titrations.

Procedure :

An aqueous solution of sample 0.1-1.0 m. mole of the mercaptan was pipetted (or a corresponding weight itself was weighed) into a 150 ml Erlenmeyer flask. Sample, if insoluble in water, was dissolved in 15 ml of 99% acetic acid and sufficient water was added at the time of titration so as to give an acid concentration between 30-50% v/v. At high acetic acid concentrations the end point was not of sharpest type. 1 ml of 1% starch sol (along with 1 ml of 2*N* hydrochloric acid when iodine cyanide was being used as titrant) was added and titrated with 0.05*N* solution of the oxidant; the end point being shown by a blue colour of starch-iodine.

TABLE 1

Sample	% RSH Recovery*			
	ICl	IBr	ICl ₃	ICN
2-Mercaptopropionic acid	100.2	100.5	100.5	100.4
Toluene α -thiol	99.8	99.9	99.8	100.1
2-Diethylamino ethane thiol	100.1	100.5	100.5	99.7
Mercaptoacetic acid	100.0	100.4	99.8	100.1
Allyl thiol	100.2	99.8	99.7	100.1
2-Mercaptoethanol	100.1	99.8	99.8	99.7
Mercaptoethyl ammonium chloride	100.2	99.9	100.2	99.7
Ethane thiol	100.2	100.1	100.2	99.9
1-Butane thiol	100.1	99.9	100.1	100.2
1-Pentane thiol	99.9	99.7	99.9	100.1
1-Propane thiol	100.2	100.1	100.2	99.8
Benzene thiol	100.1	100.1	100.1	99.8
Thiobenzoic acid	100.2	99.9	100.2	100.0

* Average of six determinations, % recovery takes account of purity determined iodometrically.

In potentiometric titrations aqueous or dilute acetic acid solution of sample taken in a 100 ml beaker and titrated with 0.05*N* solution of the oxidant, solutions being stirred after each addition using a platinum indicating electrode and a saturated

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF FOREIGN SUBSTANCES IN TITRATION OF MERCAPTANS

Sample titrated	Titrant	Add. compound	Molar ratio added compd/ RSH	RSH* recovery %
1-Butane thiol	ICl	Potassium bromide	5 : 1	100.3
	IBr	Diphenyldisulphide	6 : 1	100.0
	ICN	Potassiumcyanide	53 : 1	100.2
	ICl ₃	Ethyl acetate	36 : 1	100.2
Mercaptoacetic acid	ICl	Carbon-disulphide	4 : 1	100.4
	ICl	Acrylonitrile	9 : 1	100.0
	ICN	Bromobenzene	68 : 1	100.0
	ICl ₃	Cinnamic acid	4 : 1	100.0
Diethylamino thane thiol hydrochloride	IBr	Diethyl sulphone	7 : 1	100.0
	ICN	Diphenyl sulphide	28 : 1	100.1
	IBr	Glucose	10 : 1	100.0
	ICl ₃	Diacetone alcohol	12 : 1	100.5
Thiobenzoic acid	ICl	Propyleneglycol	9 : 1	100.4
	ICN	Diethylaniline	4 : 1	99.7
	IBr	Sulphosalicylic acid	4 : 1	100.3
	ICN	Thiophene	8 : 1	100.5
2-Mercapto propionic acid	IBr	Bromobenzene	18 : 1	100.2
	ICl ₃	Methylacrylate	8 : 1	100.0
	ICN	Diphenylthiourea	5 : 1	100.4
	ICl	Sulphur	5 : 1	100.0
	IBr	Acetaldehyde	12 : 1	100.0
	ICN	Dichlorobronzene	8 : 1	100.3

* Average of 2 determination % recovery takes into account of previously determined purity of sample.

calomel reference electrode. The point of equivalence was shown by a large potential jump.

Results and Discussion

The results, for the determination of mercaptans using visual indicator method are summarised in Table 1. The results obtained by potentiometric

titration agreed with the visual indicator results within $\pm 0.3\%$. To check the accuracy of the proposed procedure, mercaptans were determined by independent iodometric⁷ and acetylation procedures⁸ and the purity thus estimated agreed within analytical precision with those obtained by the reagents under investigation. Table 2 summarises the effect of various foreign substances on mercaptan titration. The interferences studied include compounds that cause interference in other methods and compounds containing other sulphur functional groups. Thio-carbonyl compounds, sulphide and sulphocyanide ions interfere. With mercaptans having a carboxyl group on a carbon atom to the mercapto group, overoxidations are significant.

Under the described conditions of titration, bromine monochloride and cyanogen bromide, in which monopositive bromine is the oxidizing species, tend to overoxidize mercaptans thus rendering them unsuitable.

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References

1. J. CIHALIK and D. VAVREINOVA, *Chem. Listy*, 1955, **49**, 693.
2. E. SCHULEK and K. BURGER, *Talanta*, 1958, **1**, 147.
3. E. SCHULEK and K. BURGER, *Talanta*, 1958, **1**, 219.
4. F. E. KAGAN and Y. A. FIALKOV, *Trudy Komissii Anal. Khim. Akad. Nauk, S.S.S.R., Otdel Khim. Nauk*, 1954, **5**, 237.
5. H. T. COMASTRI, *Anales Soc. quim. argentina*, 1937, **27**, 45.
6. A. I. VOGEL, *A Text Book of Pract. Org. Chem.* E.L.B.S. 1968, p. 497.
7. J. W. KIMBALL, R. L. KRAMER and E. E. REID, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1921, **43**, 1199.
8. G. H. SCHENK and J. S. FRITZ, *Anal. Chem.*, 1960, **32**, 987.